

Climate change adaptation through digital soil–water management in soils with restrictive subsoil

At the experimental orchard of the Faculty of Agriculture and Food Sciences, University of Sarajevo, a digital soil–water management system was introduced as a climate adaptation measure. The system improved water-use efficiency, optimized fertilization, reduced labor demand, and enhanced fruit quality compared with conventional irrigation.

Climate change in Bosnia and Herzegovina is reflected in rising temperatures, frequent droughts, and irregular precipitation, placing pressure on perennial fruit production. Orchards are particularly vulnerable due to high water demand and dependence on stable soil–water relations. These risks intensify soils with restrictive subsoil layers identified at the experimental site.

The soil is of alluvial origin, with a 0–25 cm clay loam horizon and a compacted subsoil layer at 25–40 cm, with bulk density up to 1.6 g cm^{-3} . Compaction caused by intensive cultivation and heavy machinery restricts root penetration, reduces infiltration and aeration, and limits effective rooting depth. As a result, drought stress develops rapidly, while intense rainfall increases the risk of water accumulation above the compacted layer, reducing nutrient uptake and yield stability.

A digital irrigation and fertigation system was implemented through the EU4AGRI project “*Smart Systems in Agriculture – Responding to 21st Century Challenges*.” Soil moisture sensors installed within the root zone monitor volumetric water content and transmit data in real time to a central unit that automatically initiates irrigation when predefined thresholds are reached.

Water and nutrients are delivered precisely through drip irrigation, and the system stops once optimal conditions are restored. Although it does not eliminate soil compaction, digital soil–water management enables precise regulation within the limited rooting zone, reducing drought and waterlogging risks and supporting climate-resilient orchard production.

Figure 2. Overview of soil moisture sensor installation, automatic fertigation units, pump, filtration system and water reservoir within the digital soil–water management

KEYWORDS

soil-water management, restrictive subsoil layer, climate change, orchard, experimental field

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